

THE PERSON IS THE URN OF THE CLASSIC MUSK AND COMES IN MATURITY

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Abstract. Music has a great positive effect on the mental and moral development of children. That is why music lessons are first of all educational lessons. The name of the science is not only the method of listening to music, but also the method of music education. In order to study in the content of the new program, the musician needs to improve his musical and theoretical knowledge.

Key words: Music, children, lesson, education, methodology, program, listener, theoretical knowledge.

Music is a type of art that is widely used in our cultural life and plays an important role in the development of human personality. Music education is one of the main and complex aspects of the education of sophistication, and it encourages the correct perception and framing of the beautiful things around. Music equips a person with high taste and forms a spiritual outlook. Music has the ability to have a strong influence on human nature, and it is an important means of introducing students to the world of sophistication and moral education.

There are some changes in the discipline of children, there are differences between the child's desire and ability. All of these require high skills and education from the listener. In this case, it will be good for the students to rely on the knowledge and skills they have acquired in the classroom and on vital evidence. For this, it is necessary to carry out the content of the lesson with life. In the process of teaching and listening to music, Kushik sings excerpts from the works and tunes his voice. It is necessary to explain the performance methods in detail. It is necessary to give children a clear understanding of the fact that music is an artistic reflection of each historical period. On this basis, a brief history of Uzbek music can be presented by comparing musical instruments and Uzbek folk music genres, statuses, and modern classics. For example: "Sashmakom" is the brotherhood of the Tajik and Uzbek peoples. It is necessary to introduce and compare the compositional works created on the basis of folk music with modern music in terms of their symbol, the fact that they are multi-instrumental instruments and can be used by other peoples. analysis will give good results. In the sixth grade, the vocal range of sleepers is I- for voices. For II-voices (Sikich- Re2) it is appropriate to teach the children to sing two voices in the period. Because at this moment, the period of mutation begins. Before the mutation period, the difference between the voices of boys and girls is not noticeable. "Teaching a puppy during the mutation requires a lot of responsibility. It is necessary to pay attention to the work of preserving the voice of the puppies during the lesson, in order to adapt the voice capabilities of the puppies.

Do not tire the voices by spending the main part of the lesson on singing. Separating the sleepers into two voices is an important means of training the puppies into two voices and adapting them to their voices. Choral singing, music, music literacy, music listening activities, analysis of works are logically connected. Based on the new program, the theme of the year, the theme of the quarter and the theme of the lesson are connected with each other.

During this period, the voice of boys gradually changes to a masculine voice, and the voice of girls gradually changes to the voice of mature women. The vocal cords in the throat of young children become swollen, reddened, swellings may appear. As a result, the range is reduced, and it

becomes difficult to sing in high pitches. Fatigue occurs quickly. Teaching singing to boys and girls during the period of transition requires responsibility. It is necessary to adapt the puppets to the children's vocal capabilities during the lesson, and carefully teach them to preserve their voices. Singing in two voices is an important means of voice education, clearly distinguishing vocal parts. There are also changes in the discipline of children. Emotional awakenings cause harmonic changes in the body to decrease interest in the lesson. During this period, the listener should skillfully connect the content of the musical works with our life, teach moral and beauty education through it and connect the content of the lesson with other subjects.

Performing vocal-choir work and listening to music based on the knowledge and skills acquired in classes and life experience will give good results. The methods of raising a puppy in the 7th grade do not differ from the general methods. When choosing music, works that are more complex in terms of content are lost.

Students will get acquainted with Uzbek folk songs, makoms, classical songs, yalla and lapar, the content of folk music, local styles, and study the structure, history. Sing classic songs, sing makoms, enjoy the masterpieces of Uzbek folk music they get The theme of the year in the seventh grade: "Local folk music styles. A general understanding of positions".

It is appropriate to study the studied works based on a certain topic in order to create an artistic and figurative overall impression. Such topics can be connected with a certain content, based on one or several lessons, the types of performance and its means of expression. For example: "Lad nima", "Local music styles", "Makom", "Big song genre", "Shashmakom". and pleasure, music and singing training should be taken into account, the basis of musical education for students is to sing in a choir. In other words, voice maintenance and special vocal-choir exercises, that is, between the sounds of three tones, low or high, without a chord in parts of the fifth or octave scale. , it is of great importance to adjust the voice by saying excerpts from kushiks. When listening to music and singing kushiks, it consolidates all the theoretical information obtained from the field of music in the process of training. In the process of teaching kushiks, by expressively performing a melodious work, the introduction of small interesting images, the genre of the work Conversation plays an important role in terms of means of expression. During the seven-year study period, as a result of working in the field of music, students acquire musical literacy, are able to analyze music consciously, participate in artistic amateur circles, listen to great musical works on radio and television, music, classes, and concerts, and are people who truly love music. they are enough.

The public affairs plan of the music player must be approved by the school administration. The plan of public and musical activities is drawn up in cooperation with the music teacher and the director of educational and spiritual affairs of the school, taking into account the age and interests of the students, holidays, meetings, events. In this, the musical ability of the singers is taken into account. Each of the mass music lessons should be carried out on the basis of a specific, developed plan. Depending on the type of training, its main purpose, features, content of the repertoire, opportunities of the school, invited guests are taken into account and students are attracted. Tugarak independently prepares the work plan based on the needs, requests and capabilities of the listener. The singer selects singers based on their musical ability, desire, interest, and voice, and creates different songs, working in groups 2-3 times a week. It is the basis of Tugarak work. Pupils who are capable of tutoring, curious and actively participate in their classes are selected. In the lesson, the ability and interest of each child is taken into account, and they are attracted to one or another musical instrument.

LITERATURE

1. Гулов С. Н. Музыка и её воздействие на психическую деятельность человека //Вестник науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 21-2 (99). – С. 89-92.
2. Гулов С. Н. Современное преподавание музыки. Подходы и инновации //Проблемы педагогики. – 2020. – №. 3 (48). – С. 22-24.
3. Гулов С. Н. Структура формирования отношений, особенности воздействия чувство, в области музыкального образования //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 651-655.
4. Gulov S. N. Senior Lecturer of the Department Music Education of Bukhara State University //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 198-202.
5. Gulov S. N. European Journal of Innovation in Nonformal Education (EJINE). – 2022.
6. Gaybulloyevich N. F., Karimovna N. N., Abdukarim o'g'li S. A. UZLUKSIZ TA'LIMDA O'ZBEK XALQ QO'SHIQLARINING TUTGAN ORNI VA TARBIYAVIY ANAMIYATI //TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 59-62.
7. Нуруллаев Ф. Г. Случайный выбор качественных характеристик материала по музыки или порядок его изложения в процессе создания музыки или исполнения опуса //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 588-593.
8. Нуруллаев Ф. Г. Интерактивные уроки музыки по программы STEAM //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 595-601.
9. Нуруллаев Ф. Г. Значение Фольклёрной Музыки В Воспитание Детей //Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – Т. 12. – С. 189-193.
10. Рахмонова В. Р., Нуруллаев Ф. Г. Особенности использования современных компьютерных программ в организации профильных предметов по музыки //Science and Education. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 4. – С. 904-911.
11. Хабибуллоева Г. Х., Нуруллаев Ф. Г. МУЗЫКА КАК ОРУДИЯ ВОСПИТАНИЯ ДЕТЕЙ РАННЕГО ВОЗРАСТА //Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 60-65.
12. NURULLAYEV F. СОДЕРЖАНИЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ БУХАРСКИМ НАРОДНЫМ ПЕСНЯМ В МУЗЫКАЛЬНОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2022. – Т. 22. – №. 22.
13. NURULLAYEV F. Интерактивные уроки музыки по программы STEAM //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2022. – Т. 20. – №. 20.
14. Шамсиев Ш. И. Формы организации музыкального общения //Вестник науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 21-2 (99). – С. 71-74.
15. Шамсиев Ш. И., Солиев А. А. Основы хорового пения на уроках музыки //Проблемы науки. – 2021. – №. 1 (60). – С. 55-57.
16. Рахимов Р. Н. Музыка как наука для формирования личности и основа организации музыкального образования и воспитания //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 4. – С. 1588-1593.
17. Рахимов Р. Н. О дидактических функциях сольфеджио при обучении теории музыки //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 776-781.

18. Рахимов Р. Н. Учебная мотивация у школьника, через пения в хоре //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 4. – С. 1570-1575.
19. Абдуллаев, С. С., Бакаев, Ш. Ш., Остонова, Г. Р., & Шарипов, Ш. Ш. (2021). Орнаментальная символика в народном декоративно-прикладном искусстве Бухары. *European science*, (2 (58)), 17-19.
20. Абдуллаев, Сухроб Сайфуллаевич. "ЭСТЕТИКА ЦВЕТА В ВОСПИТАНИИ ПЛАСТИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ АРХИТЕКТОРА." *PEDAGOGS journali* 1.1 (2022): 384-386.
21. Абдуллаев С. С., Шарипов Ш. Ш. ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ТВОРЧЕСКОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА СТУДЕНТОВ СРЕДСТВАМИ НАРОДНОГО ДЕКОРАТИВНО-ПРИКЛАДНОГО ИСКУССТВА //XXI ASRDA INNOVATION TECHNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 80-85.
22. Абдуллаев С. С. РОЛЬ СРЕДНЕВЕКОВОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ ВОСТОКА В СОЗДАНИИ СЮЖЕТОВ МИНИАТЮРЫ СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ //Inter education & global study. – 2023. – №. 2. – С. 100-108.
23. Laue S., Abdullaev S. S. Legends and True Stories about the Samanid Mausoleum //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 308-311.
24. Botirov, J. S., Bakaev, S. S., Avliyakulov, M. M., Shirinov, A. L., & Abdullaev, S. S. (2021). The same goes for art classes in private schools specific properties. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government Vol, 27(2)*.
25. Abdullayev¹ S. F., Abdullayev S. S. TRANSLATION OF CULTURAL VALUES IN THE ARTISTIC HERITAGE OF TRADITIONAL APPLIED ARTS OF BUKHARA.
26. Абдуллаев С. С. РОЛЬ СРЕДНЕВЕКОВОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ ВОСТОКА В СОЗДАНИИ СЮЖЕТОВ МИНИАТЮРЫ СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ //Inter education & global study. – 2023. – №. 2. – С. 100-108.
27. Jurayevich J. K., Sayfullayevich A. S. THE UNIQUE OF BUKHARA JEWS IN THE DYE INDUSTRY AND WEAVING CRAFT //Euro-Asia Conferences. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 48-53.
28. Sayfullayevich A. S. CHALLENGES OF TRAINING FINE ARTS TEACHERS IN THE PRESENT //International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics. – 2023. – С. 348-353.
29. Abdullaev S., Mamatov D. Pedagogical foundations in the teaching of folk arts and crafts of Uzbekistan in the training of teachers of fine arts //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 420. – С. 10019.
30. Umarova S. Традиционное искусство Бухары: истоки и преемственность //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 7. – №. 7.
31. Pirnazarov G. F., Mamurova F. I., Mamurova D. I. Calculation of Flat Ram by the Method of Displacement //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 35-39.
32. Olimov S. S., Mamurova D. I. Directions For Improving Teaching Methods //Journal of Positive School Psychology. – 2022. – С. 9671–9678-9671–9678.

33. Aminov, A. S., Mamurova, D. I., & Shukurov, A. R. (2021, February). Additional and didactic game technologies on the topic of local appearance. In *E-Conference globe* (pp. 34-37).
34. Olimov S. S., Mamurova D. I. Information Technology in Education //Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 17-22.
35. Mamurova D., Khusnidinova N. Didactic possibilities of using computer graphics programs in the educational process //BIO Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2024. – T. 84. – C. 02020.
36. Mamurova D. I., Ibatova N. I., Badieva D. M. The importance of using the keys-stadi innovative educational technology method in training the image module of geometric shapes //Scientific reports of Bukhara State University. – 2020. – T. 4. – №. 1. – C. 335-338.
37. Khodjayeva N. S., Yakhyayeva M. T. Calculate Exact Integrals in the Visual Basic Window of Excel //International Journal on Orange Technologies. – 2021. – T. 3. – №. 3. – C. 172-177.
38. Khodjayeva, Nodira. "THE URGENCY OF AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN PROSPECTIVE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING." *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры* 3.5 (2023): 77-80.
39. Xodjayeva N. S. et al. KOMPYUTER GRAFIKASI NING INFORMATSION JAMIYATDAGI AHAMIYATI, RO'LI VA O'RNI //ZAMONAVIY TA'LIM: MUAMMO VA YECHIMLARI. – 2022. – T. 1. – C. 74-77.